

RECORDS OF SOME COUSHCHETS IN THE STATE RESERVE OF SURKHON

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада йўқолиб кетиш арафасида турган ва жуда кам ўрганилган бурама шохли тоғ эчкиси ёки морхўр ҳақида кузатиш ва таҳлиллар қисқагина баён қилинган. Мавзунинг долзарблиги шундаки, она табиатимизнинг бугунги аҳволи қониқарли даражада эмаслиги ҳаммамизга маълум ва “ҳалокат сигнали”ни биринчи бўлиб ҳайвонот дунёси чалиб беряпти. Биз бу сигнални ўз вақтида эшитиб, керакли чораларни кўксак албатта инсониятнинг умри янада узайиши айни ҳақиқатдир.

Калит сўзлар: Кўхитанг тоғ тизмаси, Сурхон давлат кўриқхонаси, Морхўр, морхўрлар шохи, гавда тузилиши, морхўрлар туёғи, популяция, ижобий тенденция, экологик муҳит, овчилик, рацион, ирсият, ўзгарувчанлик.

Annotation: this article briefly describes the observations and analysis about the twisted horned mountain goat or morkhor, who stood on the eve of extinction and studied very little. The relevance of the topic is that it is known to all of us that the present state of Mother Nature is not at a satisfactory level, and the first to hear the “signal of destruction” is sounded by the animal world. If we hear this signal in time and take the necessary measures, then of course it is the same fact that the life of mankind will be even greater.

Keywords: Kohitang mountain range, Surkhon State Reserve, Morkhor, morkhor Horn, gavda structure, morkhor hoof, population, positive trend, environmental environment, hunting, ration, heredity, variability.

Burama belongs to the family of horned mountain goats or morkhor mountain goats, in honor of the Scottish scientist Hugh Falconer lot. In the world called *Capra falconeri*, it is a low-numbered species with one of 12 subspecies, only preserved in the natural state of Uzbekistan in the state reserve of Surkhon, included in the Red List of international TMXI[NT], a local subspecies standing on the verge of extinction.

The morgue belongs to the family of a pair of ungulates (*Artiodactula*), a young constellation of crossbows (*Ruminantia*), cubits (*Bovidae*).

It is also called the “Bukhara or the Tajik morgue”. The reason for this so-called is that it was originally recorded in the territory of the Emirate of Bukhara, and in these mountainous areas the Tajik nation lived more. Its obvious difference from other animals is that these are twisted branches in their buckles. There are 2 hypotheses in the so – called morkhor, in the first one Persian means “Mor – snake, Hor-eating”, that is, “snake-eating animal”, a century before that, the local population of Hatton believed that the morkhors eat snakes and search for

snakes, while the people who are bitten by snakes recover from morkhor meat, and even bezoar stones (sometimes in the winter of herbivorous animals for some 2 – according to the hypothesis “Mor - Afgan (pushtuncha) snake, akbur-Shokh”, that is, it also means a horned animal similar to a snake (in some literature it is also said that it is derived from the Urdu language).

Morkhors are distributed in the mountains of the north-west of India, in the mountains of Kohitang in eastern Pakistan and Afghanistan, Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan, in the mountains between the south-west of Tajikistan, the Panzh and the Wahsh rivers. Since morkhors have a certain social significance in the life of the inhabitants of these states, this animal is also considered a national symbol of Pakistan. To date, there are about 1000 heads in Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan, 3000 heads in Tajikistan, and around 3000bash in Pakistan, and they can be said to have silzhish on the positive side in their population.

In Uzbekistan, only threeraydi in the territory of the Kohitang mountain range. Although it is noted in some literature that Bobotog also has a low number of triplets, according to our studies, the morchors in the Bobotog territory are now completely absent, since they were completely exterminated in the 50-ies of the last century. (But there is an opportunity to restore representatives of this species again under strict control in the Bobotag region.).

This species lives at an altitude of 1500-2500 meters above sea level on the Rocky, toshkarnizli, sparse arches of the Kohitang Mountain, which are difficult to walk (living in such conditions is the main reason for their arrival to this day, and persecution for competitors is dangerous). In winter, it falls below sea level to 1300-1100 meters, avoiding thick snow cover, the reason for this is such factors as the difficulty of obtaining nutrients at high, the beginning of spring from low, the beginning of grass to grow in low-lying areas of the sun.

Negative changes in the world's ecological environment have not bypassed the morkhors either, so their number has sharply decreased as a result of the demand for more meat and less antiquated Horn. If we look at the recent past, the famine and famine that occurred in the conditions of Uzbekistan due to the war and drought in history have shown its impact. Especially during the Famine of the Second World War, as a result of the bare hunting of the inhabitants of the villages near the reserve area, the inhabitants of the villages, the morkhors, around 20-30 heads in the Kohitang territory, the Morkhors were kept alive in the Kampirtepa section Machellisoy (a place in the form of a fort surrounded by natural rock), where The local people also note that today's morchors have increased from those. In addition, the infectious disease, which spread among the Morgans in 1970-th year and 2014-th year, also had a serious negative impact on their number. But now, as a result of the well-established work, the number of morkhors exceeds 600 heads in the state reserve of Surkhon, and this can be called a situation with a positive trend.

In the morgue, gavda is compact, the physique is very handsome, and the takas themselves know this, and thanks to this, too, often come out on the rock,

twisting in the image of “proud olifta, who put himself a building”. It is noted that the male is taller than the female, the body length is 140-170 CM, the height of the YAG'rin is 100 cm, the living weight is about 80-120 kg, the average in the Free State is 10-12 years, in captivity it lives up to 19 years. An ornament that shows them salutary-this is considered a surprise Horn. The branches form a spiral or screw-shaped twine once in 3-4 years, and many world records say that in very adults the age is up to 1,5 M , but in the history of the Surkhon state reserve it is noted that it flies up to 70 cm, along the edge up to 110-115 CM(t. Kholikov article "ecological features of rare domesticated animals that meet in the Kohitang mountains"). Age is also measured by the number of twists of the branches. Their abundant hunting is due to the same branches for the developed world, if we have meat in them.

Females kaltarak up to 80 cm, Weight is also up to 40-60 kg, the branches are short 30 cm and back are curved.

The color of the skin is changeable, the color of the grass that dries in the hot season, the color of the mountain-stones in the cold season, the legs are white or Ola to the knees(in the people's language is a jack russell terrier or white), the snow is white, against the background of mountain areas it is more difficult to (In wild animals, the color of protection is important, and in the rooms it does not matter, because they always live in the protection of man. In the mornings, the top is dark, the bottom is flowing, harmonizing them with the color of the natural environment, protecting them from enemies. Just the fact that they come in the same color – this is an indication that the characters are transferred firmly to the offspring, that is, the heredity is strong, and the chances of survival of other colors are low, and the most favorable color is chosen for the areal. For example, in pedigree animals, let's say, in domesticated goats, goats of different colors and even without horns (bald), the encounter of a very large udder has become natural for everyone, and everyone has accepted this as normal.)

Large takas begin to jump from the end of April, and this situation continues until the end of July, at this time interval they appear white and walk in the “White Taka title”.

The head of the morhors is small and light, the ears are also relatively small and steep, and in the tame goats the ears are large and hanging. This difference in the ears is due to the fact that the ability of the morgue to hear is very strongly developed. Long horns perform a protective function, are of great importance both from the external and internal enemy, and in the “war of procreation”.

The muscles of the neck are very strongly developed, because they are required to carry horns of this size and not lose vigilance. The fact that the snow was pulled, the tail was bald, the legs were relatively long and barely shared, and the absence of a tail in the goats also gives such comfort that the design is light, compact, the speed of excitation increases. But he can not run far away, it was observed that half a kilometer of his breath was clogged when he was chased by

dogs, and this is their drawback, it is possible that this thing appeared after getting rid of the enemy without much running quickly in the mountains-stones. The hooves of the morgue are considered to have a specific structure. Because the edge of the hoof is made up of a hard mug, the middle of which is a soft material, which gives them an advantage that makes it possible to walk freely on the rocky surface, that is, if the hoof is firmly fixed on the stone, since the middle is gentle, it completely touches the surface of the stone, resulting in

Heredity, variability, natural selection serve only to the wild animals themselves, their growth, development, improvement and, in short, adaptation and survival in this environment. In domesticated animals, these phenomena are observed differently, as a result of the hereditary interference of artificial selection and variability with some percentage, domesticated animals are transformed, and the productivity, appearance and other strict requirements of Man are more precisely the result of human interests, a surge of great changes occurs. Ultimately, wild animals retain their original state, but it is also observed that domesticated animals change and, as a result of nausea, they do not look like their ancestors at all. Because the ration of domesticated animals is accompanied by a strong, enriched concentrate of man, artificial biological supplements, the addition of cooked nutrients and hormones and vitamins, the tearing of the goiter of goats and sheep in the process of domestication, the increase in the size of the mammary glands, the contraction of the legs, the decrease in the tendons in the legs, the, as a result of an increase in the volume of the stomach and a decrease in the risk of evasin stress, large hormonal changes occur in the body, the appearance of large, spotless, phlegmatic animals. But heredity in the morgue is such a strong influence that, according to the experience of the local people, only morkhor is born when a morkhor is put on domesticated goats. So how did the Morgans achieve this? How do they pour blood and keep the offspring in the same appearance? This can be explained as follows: in the mating season The arrival of the best, large, powerful takas from Turkmenistan and the blood transfusion through them, as well as the "victory in the war" of the local most salty takas, as a result of the fertilization, the "strengthening of blood" occurs, that is, the monoduragay or the Chatting of relatives, and thus the species firmly retains its signs, transmits a foothold to generations, we do not mean that For example, in the 80-ies of the last centuries among the Morgans came signals that there is a hornless, a bald taka is also met (in the Vandob department there is a hornless (a bald taka), but scientific workers have not yet encountered).

Morkhors live a life united into herds. Basically, they spend the mating season from November to December and get married in April to May (this season can also be pushed sometimes for certain reasons). Morhors are serpentine animals, which in the first few years give birth to one, and later two, and even three. This ability is also one of the main features in the preservation of the species. But 1-year-old female goats, that is, the teeth never mate and do not give birth, but we

know that in domesticated goats, the early births give birth at the 1-th year itself, even if the teeth are not even 100%.

Morkhors in the state reserve of Surkhon recorded nutrition with 32 species of plants growing in the Kohitang mountains(t. Kholikov article "ecological features of rare domesticated animals that meet in the Kohitang mountains"). Especially the leaves and branches of almonds and almonds are their favorite absorbents. In the years from spring Seryogin was observed to be relatively lean in the fat, arid years in the Morrows.

In the morgue, the testicle is small, in the room takas, the anchovies are large. The role of the testicle in ensuring the quality of the offspring is very large, in our opinion, the fact that the morhors are in motion Day and night improves blood circulation, even small testicles are able to guarantee the quality of the seed, on account of the swelling of these organs in the room goats ensure full fulfillment of this task.

Studies in female morchors have shown that the tissue of the mammary glands in the udder is less dense, connective and muscular tissues are strongly developed, in the chambers the mammary glands are strongly developed, especially during lactation (lactation). The above differences in male and female morphemes, that is, the lightness of the construction, are also very important for avoiding the enemy. In addition, the period of mating and childbirth in the morgue is strictly planned for a favorable season, that is, during the autumn and winter, when breastfeeding is reduced, it pairs, gives birth in the spring season, when the grass-dying increases, and it takes its children to the adult without suffering. Most domestic animals are able to breed under human support in any season of the year.

Since morhors have been considered as hunting animals for centuries, we have also considered it appropriate to think about their meat and want to bring some notes. When analyzing the quality of meat, it is not profitable to compare the meat of wild and domesticated, pedigree animals. First of all, it is necessary to lay down to adapt and serve so that the members of the animal body can live in all, whether they are wild or domesticated. But since the capture of meat-eating domestic animals has been taught, until now, a person has been subjected to mutilation as a result of an unconscious or conscious methodological selection and chatter, a person's strict plan-based Talab, an early maturation, a huge change in the histological structure of muscles and the distribution of fats throughout the body. This is what led to the fact that the meat of these tame animals is more delicious than wild relatives. The fact that the fat layer of the teriosti in the morgue is sluggish in relation to the domesticated goat and sheep determines that their meat is not sweet, that is, in a word, the meat of the morgues is not sweet, from it the meat of the domesticated goat and sheep is tastier especially the sense that the sheep breeds. The sweetness of the meat of the sheep of the surkhon fortress is explained by the abundance of fat in them. The fact is that the morgue in any case can not press the place of the goat, and

therefore the sheep. Well, then, what is the outbreak of our people on the meat of the morgue? This can be explained as follows: hunting hash and free meat (for hunters), migraines to wild and antiquities (psychology of puddles), eating one more of the basic illusions IS "claim" (this is the illusion of hunters and some "healers", because therefore some of them from behind will make a profit) and so on...

In summary, morhors are low-number animals that need protection, and it is the task of each of us to make a contribution or at least keep the current number stable in the event that the continuation of scientific research on them is the work of scientific personnel.

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